

Improvisation of Civic Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education to Form Students' Pattern of Communication

Lili Halimah, Yayuk Hidayah, Dinie Anggraeni Dewi, Dianasari

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 04, 2018</p> <p>Accepted: June 27, 2018</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20681194</p> <p>Keywords : CivicVirtue, Communication Pattern, Young Generation</p>	<p><i>This study described the communication patterns of students and Civic Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education. This study was conducted because of the concern over the communication patterns of students today. This study used descriptive qualitative method and conducted at Ahmad Dahlan University and College of Teacher Training and Education (STKIP) Pasundan Cimahi. The data was collected through interview, observation, documentation, and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). Data were analyzed using principals Miles and Huberman as data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The results showed that the communication patterns of students in Higher Education were influenced by two things, namely 1) environmental factors and 2) knowledge. It can be said that the fostering of Civil Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the pattern of communication of the younger generation has been in the process of fostering Community Virtues that involved democratic values, self-control, and prioritizing the interests of plurality. The Civic Virtue in the Civic Disposition category involved responsibility, self-discipline, respect the human rights, willingness to listen, negotiate, and compromise. In addition, the Civic Virtue in the Civic Commitment category involved a commitment to the exercise of democratic citizenship rights, responsibility for democratic citizenship, constitutionalism, and tendency to participate politically.</i></p>

Introduction

Communication is an activity that cannot be avoided. In communication, sentence analysis has become a tradition in all languages to divide the analysis into primary and secondary parts (Farruxovna & Bahodirovna, 2020). Communication is an integral part of the system and structure of social life in human and society. Human communication can be seen in every aspect of daily life, such as waking up in the morning until human come back to sleep at night. Even, in a company or organization, social interaction and social information can describe the achievement in a certain period of time (Setyahuni, Rr.Sri, & ayani, 2020). Furthermore, cross-routine can understand the unique characteristics of individuals (Coleman, Xu, & Arment, 2020). Then, communication is basically the process of delivering messages from the communicator to the communicant (recipient of the message) that can be done through certain channels or delivered directly (Lunenburg, 2010).

Communication patterns that occur in an academic environment (e.g. campus) can be divided into formal and informal communication. (Gui, Yasin, Abdullah, & Saharuddin, 2020) asserts if and one of the problems of our students is when they lose their compass of direction regarding morals. In the education environment, the pre-school program is full of activities that support students to learn to connect and manage their lives (Bakkaloglu & Ergin, 12M). The atmosphere of formal communication can be exemplified as a lecturer who applies learning in the classroom, while non-formal pattern is communication that occurs outside the classroom. Presently, many young people are influenced by their views of the world and it contributes to the development of their creative abilities (Sharifovna, Turakulova Marjona Kiyom kizi, Ramazonovna, Narzullaevna, & kizi, 2020). The results of the study on 6,601 chats between groups of students coded into one of three categories of social content interactions (social, task, and related technology), has resulted in student chats on assignments is 55%, 30% social, and 15% related technology (Orvis, Wisher, Bonk, & Olson, 2002). Therefore, communication patterns of students can be an important part in investigating their relationship patterns.

Communication patterns in the academic environment are based on the characteristics of each faculty on each campus. (Rachmadtullah, Syofyan, & Rasmitadila, 2020) emphasizing if and education is an important tool so that it becomes an intermediary in understanding the character of each other in daily life. The positive behavior support is one of the positive approaches based on the principles of behavior analysis applied in preventing inappropriate behavior in the school environment (Olcay, Koc, Vuran, & Koksai, 12M). Related to communication patterns in the academic environment, language experiences challenges and there is a need to

collect and generalize language units to infer information about limited words (Abdugafurovna, Tursunaliyeva, & Turdievna, 2020). In its use, language in communication must have a very formal and informal pattern. However, the characteristics of each lecturer do not become obstacles to the emergence of a sense of appreciation between faculty and students. More specifically, an inclusive education is a very important element of international education thinking (Alzahrani, 2020). Additionally, the inquiry-based education approach is effective in teaching and learning (Sigirtmac, 2020). There is a need to analyze the dominance of communication patterns in the environment that the demonological vocabulary of the nominated unit does not correlate with the *denotatum*, so this is a semantic community appealing exclusively to the linguistic awareness of people (Shaxobiddinova, 2020). In particular, in linguistics, there are two points of view to be considered, namely syntax and grammar aspects (Risaliyevich, 2020). However, both aspects are not yet sufficient to generalize.

The previous research that investigates communication behavior in various research fields that vigilante in China by focusing on how the media have been adapted for online search for personal information about social distortions to restore public morality, has resulted the identification of corrupt officials and the circulation of their personal data online reinforces the study of the abuse of power and to pressure authorities towards greater accountability (Cheong & Gong, 2010). Furthermore, a research that focused on the study of democracy realizes that in implementing it in class, has resulted that the differences of opinion in class discussion are implemented to produce democratic supportive conditioning. The differences of opinion in class are needed to support the understanding of citizenship. Through previous researches, the ability to communicate opinions through the classroom can practice the nuances of democracy (McMurray, 2007).

Meanwhile, research on communication patterns to government through the internet has led to interesting empirical and theoretical results. Using this survey study, the effects of technology have produced two types, namely creating active citizens in communicating with the government and communication intensity (Bimber, 1999). A study that emphasized the role of communication in social conflict has produced social conflict with the violence that accompanies it and it is best described as evidence of communication disorders (Hamijoyo, 2001). A study on communication between the public and the government in Surabaya has showed that the Public Information Group (KIM) played a role in two-sided information that expands the program and expressed complaints and suggestions from the public (Aji, Tsurroya, & Dewi, 2018).

In facing the era of globalization in the 21st century, communication is very important and it demands good performance as a social survival today. In the era of globalization, social networking is an excellent source for users to share and exchange information about various topics (Noorullah & Mohammed, 2020). Then, in education, to evaluate academic skills, children must be in the school age and the intervention cannot begin in the pre-school period (Balikci & Melekoglu, 2020). Furthermore, the era of globalization that occurred in the 21st century requires the basic principles of learning a new system for assessing educational outcomes in order to be accepted in society (Pozilova, Marasulova, Delov, Azimova, & Rashidov, 2020). Communication patterns are part of soft skills, and the soft skills (Hamidah, 2013) are embedded in the working area and seen through good performance during the theory or practice of learning. One of the required soft skills is communication. In his research, the strength of students' soft skills on communication was 49.90%, while the weakness was 50.10% (Hamidah, 2013). Additionally, the current stage of human development occurs in a direct relationship with the process of globalization (Mardonov, Khodjamkulov, Botirova, & Shermatova, 2020). Clearly argued that communication becomes a part of students' soft skills (interpersonal skills) that is sharpened and improved through the learning process.

Based on previous relevant researches, there are various forms of communication in the 21st century that are interesting for further study. In this case, the sign that serves in distinguishing from one another is supposed to be able to identify various forms of communication (Jumaniyazovna, 2020). In more specifically, technology (especially digital devices), can be used for interesting and effective learning experiences (Almumen & Almuhareb, 2020). Therefore, a topic on developing civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education to form the communication of the younger generation in the 21st century has not been studied. This is in accordance with a study that developing the quality of education is possible in practical tasks that makes it possible for students to be able to make preparations for real life that involves the formation of communicative competencies in terms of building contacts, exchanging information, and sharing problem solving (Khudaybergenovna, Abdullayevna, Alimovna, & qizi, 2020). Therefore, this research is expected to be able to resolve gaps in the research space to generate ideas as well as to foster civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education. This research is intended to focus on students' communication patterns in 21st century and how civic virtue education through Civil Education in Higher Education takes a role in forming young generation communication in the 21st century.

The purpose of this study is to describe the pattern of communication in students and foster civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the communication of the younger generation in the 21st century. In this case, in Linguistics, all practical and theoretical grammars and syntactic analysis of speech refer to the analysis of all syntactic units involved in sentences that next become the primary and secondary parts at all stages of the entire education system (Farruxovna & Bahodirovna, 2020). Therefore, the researchers expect that

the practical benefit of this research is to contribute ideas for universities to improve the efficiency of Citizenship Education in Higher Education to form patterns of communication of the younger generation. The use of theory in establishing the basis for estimating the quality of education has been largely ignored (Akbutayevich & Abdumalikovch, 2020). Besides, the results of scientific journals do not only function as a source of information to guide practice in that field, but also as a transmitter to extract information filtered from practice (Akbutayevich & Abdumalikovch, 2020). Hence, this research is expected to be useful for further research that will

Method

This study used descriptive qualitative method that concentrated on descriptive data to produce descriptive results (Moleong, 2002). Qualitative research was intended in this study, so that the researchers could easily interpret the development of civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the communication of the younger generation in the 21st century. This research was conducted at Ahmad Dahlan University (UAD) Yogyakarta and the College of Education and Teacher Training (STKIP) Pasundan Cimahi, West Java Indonesian.

STKIP Pasundan, Cimahi		Class /Semester
1	English Department	3
2	Department of Sport and Recreation	3
Ahmad Dahlan University (UAD) Yogyakarta		Class /Semester
1	Pharmacy	International/3
2	Mathematics	A/3
3	Mathematics	B/3

The research subjects were five Citizenship Education lecturers. The data were collected through interview, observation, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and documentation.

Civic Virtue	Keywords
Civic Disposition	a) Responsible b) Self-discipline c) Human rights' respect d) Willing to listen, negotiate, and compromise.
	a) Committed on the implementation of civil democratic rights b) Committed on civil democratic responsibility c) Committed on the constitutionalism and tendency to participate politically
Civic Commitment	

Interview was conducted on several forms of questions:

- How do you show responsibility and self-discipline?
- What is your attitude when listening, negotiating, and compromising in doing the same job?
- What do you think about the implementation of democracy in Indonesia?
- What do you think about the constitution in Indonesia?
- What is your attitude towards opinion and free speech?

The observation was performed by observing the behaviors and activities that fostered the primacy of citizenship through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the communication of the younger generation in the 21st century. The researchers made a list and recorded activities in the study area. Focus Group Discussion was carried out by determining topics related to teaching the virtues of citizens through Citizenship Education in Higher Education to form the communication of young people in the 21st century. In any stage of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), each team consisted of two people. Apart from it, the documentation was intended to collect documents related to developing civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education to form the communication of the younger generation in the 21st century. Finally, to analyze data, this study used the perspective of Miles and Huberman which involved reducing data, displaying data, and drawing conclusion.

Results and Discussion

The Pattern of Students' Communication

As an effort to recognize communication patterns to students, the researchers firstly used data of documents obtained through journals, research results, books and other related resources to supplement research findings and collaborated on discussions. In his development, a child or individual developed according to their environment. In the initial stages, the researchers' effort in capturing student communication patterns was to ensure that this

research was relevant to current generation theories (Sucuoglu, Bakkaloglu, & Demir, 2020). This was done, because the current position of students was a part of generation Z, and they were already familiar with technology (Adam, 2017). Previous study (Yazici, Akman, Uzun, & Akgul, 2020) explained that by the beginning of the nineteenth century, new ideas began to emerge in education. Then, today's pattern of communication is emphasizing openness, and it is one of the patterns of generation Z communication (Husna, 2018).

The behavior of serving citizenship becomes a factor in the realization of good citizenship, and there is no exception for Generation Z. In learning, learning interaction is meaningful due to the availability of an approach (Kasemkosin, Howteerakul, Suwannapong, Tipayamongkhogul, & Pajareya, 2020). Then, the efforts to involve citizens in public policy and management are classified into four categories of citizen orientation that may influence trust participation in government institutions, moral motivation, environmental social norms and environmental influences [52]. On the other hand, in Kant's view, virtue is a good intention and it is sufficiently strong to counter conflicting desires, impulses, and tendencies (Hill, 2013). Meanwhile, in Rawls's view, a sense of justice as a civil virtue will develop naturally according to certain psychological laws as if the basic structure of society is fair.

Again with communication, the experts try to define communication from various perspectives. Type & Kelly (Vardiansyah, 2008) state that communication is the process of conveying messages in the form of words to change the behavior of others. Meanwhile, Berelson & Stainer (Vardiansyah, 2008) also stated that communication is the process of delivering information through symbols. Thus, there are several compositions in the communication element, such as communicators, messages, media, and recipients. Besides, there are three terms in the communication pattern. *First*, one-sided communication (the recipient of the message (communicant) merely acts as the recipient of the message). *Second*, two-sided communication (the exchange of functions between the recipient of the message and the recipient). *Third*, multi-directional communication (Effendy, 1989).

Phonological awareness is one of the most important skills in literacy, so that communication patterns of students can be part of a citizen behavior in society that reflect their identity (Balikci, 2020). In this case, a number of phenomena have given new complexity to the old challenges of building a legitimate and stable political order (Maclure, 2006). Then, citizen communication is still poorly understood in the mainstream of social, cultural and political development policies and practices that make it transformative (Pettit, Salazar, & Gumucio, 2009). However, communication patterns can reflect someone's personal identity. Various visual materials can be designed to teach children about skills (Cesur & Odluyurt, 2019).

Based on observation and interview on 3rd semester students at the Department of Pharmacy (International class) Ahmad Dahlan University Yogyakarta, there was a unique pattern of student communication. The tendency of a generation that was closed to technology could not be separated from its uniqueness. In terms of building relationships, the child's friendship environment could be used to support the development of friendships (Krone & Yu, 2019). Then, statistically, a study suggested that in communication, it was observed that the family had a statistically significant effect on family functioning; that was parents (Ardic & Cavkaytar, 2019). The feedback or circle communication patterns could be seen in the ownership of "Instagram" accounts for classes that were managed collectively (H. Cangara, 2006). The intention to establish an "Instagram" account was to "vent" the media from what they have experienced in class to get feedback from their classmates. Therefore, interpersonal communication as a systematic iterative sequence, was presented in this situation (Budyatna & Ganiem, 2001).

Based on these findings, the unique communication patterns of students become their specialty as citizens. However, communication cannot be treated as only factor that leads to organizational effectiveness, but if there is a lack of coherent communication, other factors will not make it up; no matter how good they are (Zalewska, 2016). As a comparison about the unique communication patterns of students, the results of the study to understand the types of challenges posed by teachers related to professional challenges resulted in six themes that focused on logistics, case load, confidence and competence, characteristics of teachers, parents, early childhood programs, accessing resources and professional support, and meeting the needs of certain children (Dinnebeil, Weber, & McInerney, 2019). However, by reflecting on communication patterns that use the platform (media), at present, it is very difficult for the practice community to select and configure appropriate communication services, because their communicative requirements are difficult to determine using web service modeling that focuses on technology and specification approaches (Moor & Weigand, 2005). On the other side about education, the roles and responsibilities of pre-school teachers are major factors in the success of educational practice (Gezer & Aksoy, 2019).

Learning to communicate with others in one's environment is very important. Learning to speak language is a complex process (MACY, 11M). The study of student communication patterns on USB YPKP on WhatsApp has resulted that the language used by WhatsApp group members was diverse, such as Indonesian and regional languages like Sundanese, Javanese, Sumatra, Betawi, and Papuan. In addition, the topic of conversation also varied. Although the dominant topic was academic, students avoided discussing and talking about political topics, because it was sensitive case (Sidik & Sanusi, 2018). In addition to using an Instagram account, the 3rd semester students at Pharmacy in international class also used Whatsapp group as a communication tool that allowed them to coordinate. Therefore, communication using various platforms is more instant. Students realize that their lives

cannot be separated from digitalization, so that they have adjusted to this change.

The goals of innovation introduced in all fields of the rapid development of science and technology are ultimately aimed at increasing the country's economic and social potential (Khodjamkulov, Botirova, & Abdishukur Shofkorov, 2020). The findings of further research are the use of language structures used by students in conveying their messages to communicate. Based on the results of interview with Mathematics (MIPA) class A and B students, found that the use of straightforward and polite language in using Whatsapp groups still existed. In the use of language, content analysis shows that more than half of children are described as typical in terms of development, while some are described as gifted and gifted by their parents, and about one-third have special educational needs (Sujitha, Jothi, & Narayanamoorthy, 2020). Meanwhile, in terms of communicating with their lecturers, students recognized that they needed to speak proportional language in accordance with the ethics of communication in the academic environment. The results of research on the consumption practices of young people in the use of technology have produced that the fundamental motivation underlying the use of communication media was connectivity. (Hernawati, Sugiharto, Purwanto, & Awalya, 2020) states that students must adapt to academic life including facing academic pressure, peer pressure, and unhealthy physical conditions due to physical and mental fatigue in performing various academic tasks. The choice of communication technology depends on the structural nature of technology in improving social relations (Behairy, Mukherjee, Ertimur, Venkatesh, & Ertimu, 2006). Based on interview, Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and documentation, it was found that students' communication patterns were influenced by several things, included the environment and knowledge.

It is predicted that in the future, there will be a change of profession in accordance with the statement of a study that changing professions/jobs from one generation to another is called social mobility (Prasanti, Rajyalakshmi, & Jayalakshmi, 2020). In this regard, the results of the study indicated that the environment influenced students' communication patterns. The environment could be classified as culture and communication atmosphere. Culture that influenced communication patterns could generally be identified by using intonation in communication. Based on observations at Ahmad Dahlan University Yogyakarta and STKIP Pasundan Cimahi, there were differences in the use of intonation of communication between one student and another student. However, there was an increase in awareness of the students to be able to adjust according to their surroundings. The results of research has found the influence of ethnic group membership and family communication environment on knowledge and disposition (Austin & Nelson, 1993). It was hypothesized that cultural individualism-collectivism, self-construction, and values would have separate effects on the use of individual communication styles in the context of low and high communication (Gudykunst et al., 1996).

Based on observations at the University of Ahmad Dahlan Yogyakarta and STKIP Pasundan Cimahi about the differences in ways of communication make a reflection that the characteristics of a person must be adjusted to the prevailing norms of society. Education in the economic process requires national education reform (Talatovna & Bahodirjanovich, 2020). A study on analyzing social-ethnic-religious differences in Southeast Asia, and the role of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) resulted in several factors causing social-ethnic and religious divergences in Southeast Asian countries: Indonesia, Myanmar, Filipina, Thailand and Malaysia (Idi, Abdullah, Pulungan, Adil, & Rohimin, 2020). The main factors are related to facilitating the context: 'inheritance' of various colonial discriminatory policies, socio-economic and political imbalances, demographics, and ethnic-minority relations. Nevertheless, as a member of the community, from everyone's environment, a thorough understanding of the organization as a comprehensive system, the formal structural nature, and the relationships of individuals acting in it are lack (Conrath, 1973). For students, communication skill is an important element of generic skills among students (Iksan et al., 2012). Through their years at university, students will be faced with situations inside and outside the lecture hall, where they must use their communication skills, such as group assignments and class presentations. Therefore, the characteristics of formal structures with communication patterns are distinguished by fashion. In the context of inquiry learning, students are required to think critically and analytically to find and solve answers to a problem, but in today's reality shows that students still cannot think critically about questions in the form of material related to their neighborhood (Arini, Suratno, & Yushardi, 2019).

Teamwork practice has changed trendy work plans in all types of organizations today (Dhas & Vetrivel, 2020). Students' communication patterns are influenced by knowledge. This means that this is about using diction in the absorption of communication messages. The results of research on the factors that affected the effectiveness of interpersonal communication Head of the Human Resources Agency in Bengkulu Province has produced that interpersonal communication patterns that were characterized by openness in various activities, support for employees, have a positive attitude towards employees and equality in carrying out tasks (Indah, 2018). Interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) on Mathematics (MIPA) students in classes A and B have resulted that communication between students during discussion has proven that the use of easily influenced language has been applied by students. On the other hand, the pattern of personal communication of lecturers through the "Messenger" application still requires training, especially in certain conditions (such as text messages without setting goals and self-introduction). Conversely, the pattern of communication between lecturers and students is balanced. During an interview with Citizenship Education lecturers at Ahmad Dahlan University,

Yogyakarta and STKIP Pasundan Cimahi, the communication between lecturers and students has been implemented and has developed a pattern of mutual respect to get effective conversation.

There are various things that can affect student communication patterns. The smallest part is family. The family is the place where power politics between the sexes are embedded and that the patriarchal discourse begins to force women to lead fringe lives without existence (Ujjwalbiswas & Banerjee, 2020). Student communication patterns that are influenced by knowledge imply that there are external factors that can influence this. Nonverbal behavior can be useful and be a tool that helps in psychotherapy or to detect simulated behavior (Ciolacu, 2014). Then, individual communication styles can guide increasing creativity (Ciolacu, 2014). The acquisition of soft skills is proven to achieve better results, because it is done in a better learning environment (Senguttuvan & M, 2020). The results of interview and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) on 3rd semester students of English Department at STKIP Pasundan Cimahi, have resulted in the majority of students proving Civic Virtue as their willingness to create effective situations in collaboration. Teachers should be able to identify and recognize the model of students' mentality in order that they can learn optimally (Prayekti, Nusantara, Sudirman, Susanto, & Rofiki, 2020). The 3rd semester student at English Department at STKIP Pasundan Cimahi argued that in reaching for an effective collaboration, students needed to negate personal interest. As result, they realized that the presence of a leader in a collaboration has become an important supporting factor in establishing an effective collaboration. The different perspective do not longer become an obstacle in collaboration, but it is more than just a positive one that should be interpreted by positive view. In this case, the students argued that the different perspective is important for them. Hence, the civic virtue of students in the category of Civic Disposition can be performed through an emphasis on the readiness in listening, negotiating, and compromising with students' personality.

Collaboration and cooperation between students have become a representation of student awareness in achieving goals. Communication is an important element in social work practices and society (Farukuzzaman & Rahman, 2019). Then, modeling communication patterns by individuals is an important challenge in communication (Burgers, 2016). On the other hand, face-to-face communication is more cohesive and personal (Jonassen & Kwon, 2001). Therefore, student's collaboration which is manifested in a small community in the classroom is the beginning of the realization of how they as citizens can play a role in social life.

Furthermore, Civic Virtue in the Civic Disposition category is self-discipline. Based on observation of students at Ahmad Dahlan University, Yogyakarta and STKIP Pasundan Cimahi, has proven that students have their way of developing Civic Virtue in the Civic Disposition category particularly in self-discipline. This was done by carrying out various activities while focusing on this goal. Students have integrity in conducting self-discipline through time discipline and the discipline of social life as a nation. Their discipline as a nation is carried out in their obedience to the norms that exist in their environment. A study of self-determination theory (SDT) proves that strong psychology supports interactive and multidimensional human characters in every socio-cultural context (Chirkov, 2009). Civic Virtue in the Civic Disposition category through Self-disciplines has provided several disciplinary methods, namely: time discipline and social life discipline. Civic Virtue has various meanings, namely courage, patience, skills, and national spirit (Syarifa, 2019). Thus, self-discipline in improving Civic Virtue in students provides a description of Civic Disposition to students.

Based on observations, interviews, and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) on 3rd semester students at the Department of Sports, Physics, and Recreation STKIP Pasundan Cimahi has resulted that students have the responsibility in actualizing awareness of certain specific tasks. Responsibility is the act of completing all tasks and ready to sacrifice (Muhammad, 2000). The existence of a class group illustrates that students are able to understand each task. The description of Citizenship Disposition to students can be identified in several behavioral details and attitude actualization. Although Civic Virtue still needs guidance and training, Civic Education is expected to be able to help in breaking away to form communication patterns. In detail, developing civic virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education can be as follows:

Table 3. Civic Virtue in Higher Education

No	Substance	Guidance on <i>civic virtue</i>
1.	The process of Citizenship Education learning implementation	Democratic value Self-control Prioritizing joint importance
2.	Civic Disposition	Being responsible Self-discipline Respect for human rights willing to listen, negotiate, and compromise
3.	Civic Commitment	Committed on the implementation of civil democratic rights Committed on civil democratic responsibility Committed on the constitutionalism and tendency to participate politically

The Improvisation of Civic Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education to Form the Pattern of Communication of the Young Generation

The conception of guidance on Civil Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the pattern of communication of the younger generation in the 21st century is based on the Article 37 paragraph (1) and (2) of Law Number 20 Year 2003 concerning the National Education System as one of the underlying the Citizenship Education paradigm in Higher Education. Learning Citizenship Education means learning Indonesia (P. Nurwardan, H.Y. Saksama, U.S. Winataputra, D. Budimansyah, Sapriya, Winarno, A. Festanto, 2016). Thus, the value of Indonesian essence is still in the learning process of Citizenship Education.

In the context of global Citizenship Education, some basic values in Civic Education which can be classified as deity, humanity, unity, citizenship, social justice, respect, peace and independence (Murdiono, 2014). In analyzing Citizenship Education, there will be many interesting elements to discuss. One of them is the Civic Virtue. Civic Virtue is the nation's actions to prioritize public interests above personal interests (Arif, 2017). The Civic Virtue consists of Civic Disposition and Civic Commitment (Syarif, 2019). The Civic Disposition is a national characteristic, while the Civic Commitment is the nation's commitment to democratic values that underlie their lives.

Fostering Civil Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in shaping the pattern of communication of the younger generation means that Citizenship Education in Higher Education is a platform in the process of fostering Civic Virtue. The results of a 2008 survey on the role of communication in the socialization of democratic citizenship to adolescents at the age of 12-17 years and their parents have resulted that participation in deliberative class activities has contributed to civic activism in the personality of the younger generation. Specifically, this survey highlights online participation channels that only focus on news and political expression through internet technology (Lee, Shah, & Mcleod, 2013). Based on the results of interview, Focus Group Discussions (FGD), and documentation, the researchers obtained the results that the promotion of Civil Virtue through Citizenship Education in Higher Education was available in the learning scheme process that involved planning, implementation, and evaluation.

Citizenship Education for Community's Virtue

Planning

Planning is the process of determining how goals, activities, and results need to be achieved. The learning planning stage is the initial stage that can influence the results achieved in learning. Learning planning as described in the Learning Plan Implementation (RPS) has a large function on the learning objectives (O. Hamalik, 2009). There are three needs in a learning plan: a resource plan, an organizational learning plan, and an implementation responsibility plan.

The results of interviews with the Citizenship Education lecturer at Ahmad Dahlan University in Yogyakarta have proven that at the planning stage, the Citizenship Education lecturer has set goals, methods, and achievements in the course. The lecturer planned the learning by arranging the RPS program starting with the learning design to achieve the learning objectives that are systematically adjusted to the higher education curriculum, and that was valid. The preparation of the ICM RPS on Citizenship Education was carried out jointly with the ICM Citizenship Education team and the RPS was compiled systematically in accordance with the preparation of the RPS guidelines and format. For the Civic ICM RPS itself, there was uniformity in its use.

Implementation

In the implementation of Citizenship Education learning, a lecturer tries to apply a learning model that can make students active. The promotion of civic virtue through civic education in the learning process is to use discussion as a learning strategy. Based on observations in class A and B of the Department of Mathematics, there were several values that can be built through the strategies implemented. These values are commitment and encouragement to make decisions and closeness in a group. Fostering the primacy of citizenship in discussion can train students' self-control and sense of responsibility towards the common interests in a group.

One of the goals in fostering civic virtue through Citizenship Education is to enhance nationalism. Social conditions and the potential for conflict are strong reasons for teaching nationalism in school (Ben-Porath, 2007). Indonesia as a large country and has the potential for conflict and require to learning nationalism. Based on interview on the 3rd semester international class at the Department of Pharmacy, students recognized that the Citizenship Education learning process could contribute critical thinking and problem solving by prioritizing the discussion.

Based on interview and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) on Mathematics students in class A and B and international classes at Ahmad Dahlan University, they have shown different results on democratic values that formed their attitudes that were prevalent when the discussion took place. The democratic values shown were appreciation and respect for differences of opinion and freedom of opinion based on responsibility, being fair in expressing opinions, and not disturbing when their friends were speaking.

Evaluation

Assessment is an important component in the education system. With the results of the assessment, the development and progress achieved by students in education can be identified. Assessment is an important element in the learning process. The success of a teacher in educating students is not only evidenced by high scores on cognitive abilities, but also from the realization of the attitude of self-awareness in students themselves. Assessment of learning in tertiary education is regulated in the National Education Standards (SNP), where the minimum criteria for study in Higher Education in all jurisdictions are listed in point (d) (Setiawan, 2013). The assessment standards outlined further in the Graduate Competency Standards are minimum qualification criteria, graduates' abilities include attitudes, knowledge, and skills stated in the Learning Outcomes (CP) formulation [31]. Furthermore, the Article 19 states that the Learning Assessment Standards are the minimum criteria of the assessment process and student learning outcomes to meet CP graduates includes: a) assessment principles, b) techniques and instruments, c) assessment mechanisms and procedures, d) implementation of assessments, e) assessment report, and f) graduation (Republik Indonesia Menristekdikti, 2015).

Based on the explanation above, the focus of assessment in this study referred to the techniques and instruments used to assess student attitudes as a form of civic virtue, and were implemented by using observation. Observations were made on all research objects, namely the international class A and B Mathematics students of the Ahmad Dahlan University and students in English Education and Sports Education at STKIP Pasundan.

Conclusion

The communication patterns of students in Higher Education are influenced by two factors, namely the environment and knowledge. Fostering the primacy of citizenship through Citizenship Education in Higher Education in forming the communication of the younger generation is in the process of learning the implementation of Citizenship Education that can foster citizenship values include democratic values and self-control, focusing on shared interests, civic dispositions that includes responsibility, independence-discipline, respect for human rights, willingness to listen, negotiate and compromise, commitment of citizens includes commitment to the implementation of democratic citizenship rights.

Recommendations

The results of this inter-university research were taken into consideration by MKU teaching lecturers for future development as expected. Communication patterns and student citizenship are transformed into characters of responsibility, self-discipline, respect for human rights, willingness to listen, negotiate, and compromise. In addition, Citizenship in the Civil Commitment category involves a commitment to the exercise of democratic citizenship rights, responsibility for democratic citizenship, constitutionalism, and a tendency to participate politically.

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Author Information

Lili Halimah

Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan (STKIP) Pasundan

Yayuk Hidayah

Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, DIY Yogyakarta, Jawa Tengah, Indonesia

Dinie Anggraeni Dewi

Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia (UPI) Kampus Cibiru, Bandung, Jawa Barat, Indonesia

Dianasari

Universitas Muhammadiyah Cirebon, Jawa Barat, Indonesia